

Speak up, work hard, and grasp every opportunity!

Report from Women in Crop Science coffee morning co-hosted by CIMMYT and AWARD

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Background

On Wednesday 30th November 2022, the CIMMYT Nairobi office held another successful Women in Crop Science coffee morning event (the third event for the group in 2022!). Different from the last two coffee morning events, we had the honor to welcome a guest speaker, the wonderful and brilliant Dr. Susan Kaaria, Director of the African Women in Agricultural Research and Development ([AWARD](#)). Through a fireside chat moderated by Dorine Odongo, the Senior Communication Manager at AWARD, we learnt a lot about Susan's career path, experiences, and her motivations in life. Susan also shared with the audience the importance of speaking up in meetings and why it is fundamental to promote and elevate ourselves as women working in crop science.

She addressed the importance of mentorship, volunteering, setting professional goals, taking opportunities, going the extra mile, and working hard. Speaking up, asking questions, and the importance of preparing in advance (for example for a job interview or a panel discussion) are key if you want to be seen and heard and want to progress in life.

Dr. Susan Kaaria, AWARD Director (*left*) and Dorine Odongo, Senior Communication Manager AWARD

Getting to know Dr. Susan Kaaria

Susan's career spans over 20 years in agricultural research and development with a personal commitment towards achieving gender equality in agriculture. This commitment came very early in her career, while working as an agricultural extension officer, where she had first-hand experience and recognized the challenges women farmers faced including access to land, information, training, and financial services. To make an impactful change in the lives of women farmers, Susan knew she needed to be better positioned to influence decisions at higher level. She therefore pursued her master's degree in agricultural economics from Iowa State University in the USA and later her PhD degree in Natural Resource Economics from the University of Minnesota, USA. She currently works to support gender-responsive agricultural research and development in Africa.

The importance of mentoring and peer-to peer-mentoring support

In her address, Susan encouraged the women in the audience (and all women) to lean on supportive mentors. In her early career, she mentioned and acknowledged two female scientists who influenced her tremendously and helped shape and guide her future. Their support both professionally and personally, led her to push boundaries, learn new skills and take up opportunities in various programs. On a personal level, she admired their independence, and agency to make decisions. Susan also strongly credited the important role and influence her mother played in her career success. She highlighted that finding or identifying and approaching the right mentor can be a challenge; but she advised women to map out their career path and be more courageous in approaching the person or people who have a similar career pathway and requesting their support to guide and mentor you. Mentors can be your supervisor, your peers or colleagues at work or a friend. Peer- to- peer mentoring support has been important in Susan's professional career and through the years she has built long-term relationships with peers that continue to invest time to support and advise her in various life stages.

Promoting and elevating women's roles, presence, and voices in crop science/research

Susan encouraged women to prepare or research in advance, be comprehensive, speak up, ask questions and work hard to set themselves apart. Her advice to women leading teams was the need to ensure they have a team that is dependable, saying "make sure your team is good at their work as this will make a difference in the goals you set, and this also allows you to excel as a leader". Regarding work-life balance, her advice to female scientists and researchers who in many cases have had to sacrifice their careers for their families, was the need to make conscious decisions not to attend every meeting or conference, to delegate when they can and have open-discussions with supervisors to get the support they need. Also talking with the mentors and peers to navigate some of the challenges they face is crucial. She highlighted how she managed working with a difficult supervisor and the importance of leaning on mentors and peers who will reaffirm you and support you during times when you question your capabilities in the workplace.

Her final remarks were as follows: "there are no shortcuts in life, do a thorough job in every assigned role you get, volunteer for tasks, you will be recognized and viewed as a hard worker, learn an additional skill, a language for instance, apply for the position you want, prepare for interviews, and expect and embrace failures and learn from those failures and finally set professional goals".

As the AWARD Director, Susan continues to support female scientists through the AWARD Fellowship program (<https://agspirations.awardfellowships.org/>). The program empowers women agricultural research scientists by their building their leadership, mentoring, and scientific research skills.

To keep up to date with the latest Women in Crop Science activities and publications, please join our Directory. For more information see: <https://womenincropscience.org/>

Attendees at the Women in Crop Science coffee morning event with Dr. Susan Kaaria (Photo: David Iraya, AWARD)